

Serum Testosterone Values and Coronary Artery Disease in Diabetes -Gender Based Study

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Abstract:

Introduction: Low Testosterone level in male diabetes population is linked with predisposition to coronary artery disease (CAD). Connection between testosterone values and severity of CAD in diabetes females is not well established. We correlated CAD with serum testosterone values in diabetes men and women. **Methods:** Cross-sectional project recruited Type-2 diabetes mellitus patients between 18-60 years posted for coronary angiogram. Patients were grouped into single, double, and triple vessel CAD based on involvement of coronary arteries. Data collected was analyzed to see the relationship between serum testosterone value, waist-hip ratio (WHR), glycemic control (HbA1c values) and extent of coronary artery disease. **Results:** Mean values were matched for both study groups by applying Independent sample t-test (2 groups). In case of statistically significant values, further post-hoc test (LSD) was employed for pair wise comparisons. Of the 165 subjects enrolled, 77.6% had CAD. Left anterior descending artery (LAD=50.3%), was commonly affected vessel. Presence of CAD was observed in diabetes with lower serum testosterone values. In females, obtuse marginal

and ramus branch involvement in CAD was statistically significantly associated with lower serum testosterone values. Glycemic control did not show statistically significant (p value = 0.454) correlation to CAD. The correlation was negative (r value = -0.124) in males and positive (r value = 0.066) in females, between WHR and testosterone levels. **Conclusion:** In type 2 diabetes men, higher serum testosterone levels were associated with protection from CAD. In type 2 diabetes women, testosterone levels did not seem to have protective effect against CAD. Poor glycemic control and lower testosterone values showed increased preponderance to CAD. WHR in males showed inverse correlation to presence of CAD. In females WHR did not show any significant association with CAD. A large sample study can give statistically significant results.

Keywords: gender difference, glycemic control, heart disease, male sex hormones, waist hip ratio

Introduction

Coronary artery disease (CAD) has a major share in global mortality. Increased prevalence of predisposing factors for CAD has dramatically increased occurrence of CAD [1]. Diabetes is a dynamic disease involving several risks associated with CAD - hyperglycemia, insulin resistance, lipid dysfunction, obesity, and hypertension. Though the relationship between these traditional risk factors and CAD is well established there is not much information on the role of non-traditional risk factors that can contribute to development or exacerbation of CAD [2,3]. Recent research has shown association of testosterone, the principal male sex hormone, to cardiovascular risk factors by altering myocardial and vascular cell behavior [4,5].

For males post 40 years of age, testosterone values drop and this fall is linked with rise in overall mortality and cardiovascular risk [6]. In 2013, Oskui et al reported men are more likely to develop CAD if they have lower levels of testosterone [7] Raza et al in 2019 [8], found diabetes with CAD showed lower values of testosterone compared to those without. Studies have concluded that serum testosterone levels are inversely related to CAD severity [9-11]. Another research projected that severity of CAD could be predicted by low serum testosterone levels independent of conventional risk factors of CAD like age, dyslipidemia, BMI, Diabetes, high blood pressure, and cigarette usage [12]. Protective role of testosterone against CAD in females, especially postmenopausal women has been reported [13-15]. The aim of this project was to study relationship among serum testosterone values, waist-hip ratio (WHR) and magnitude of coronary artery disease (CAD) in diabetes males and females.

Our study helps to attain “**goal 3**” of good health and wellbeing and “**goal 5**” of gender equality, for the betterment of our planet; as set by the United Nations General Assembly as Sustainable Development Goals in 2015.

Materials And Methods:

Sample collection:

Adult patients visiting tertiary care hospital in south Indian city between September 2018 to 2020 were included based on the following criteria:

Inclusion criteria –

- Males and females
- Known cases of type II diabetes mellitus under regular treatment diagnosed by clinicians according to the WHO guidelines.
- Aged between 18-60 years - age limit was arbitrarily considered.
- Admitted in hospital with symptoms indicating ischemic heart disease.
- Admitted for both emergency and elective angiograms were considered to attain a sample size of substantial number within the said study period.
- Those visiting the out-patient department for regular health check.

Exclusion criteria –

- not giving consent
- known cases of hypogonadism were excluded to avoid the confounding effect of pre-existing low testosterone levels. Effect of long-standing congenital sex hormone deficiency has not been studied in larger population in detail, hence the said group was excluded from the study.
- patients with previous history of cardiac ailments and /or long term regular cardiac medications, revascularization,
- known cases of prostate cancer on anti- androgens treatment,
- known cases of liver or renal dysfunction,
- those consuming medications like chlorambucil, Cisplatin, Cyclophosphamide, Busulphan, Procarbazine, Suramin, Ketoconazole, SSRIs, 5 alpha reductase inhibitors, Cimetidine, Glucocorticoids.

Ethical consideration:

Study was initiated after the approval and clearance from institutional Ethics Committee, Kasturba Medical College, Mangalore (IEC KMC MLR 09-18/259). All the procedures implemented were along the ethical standards. The permission from the Medical Superintendent of the hospital to conduct the study was taken. Patients were informed about the study, related queries were clarified and an informed consent was procured prior to onset of the study. The nature and purpose of study were explained to the patients in a language they understood. These patients were then invited to participate in the study. All the collected information was kept confidential. To ensure subject data anonymity, identifying details were not linked to study data in accordance with guidelines for research on human subjects. This project was performed in line with the Declaration of Helsinki.

Methodology:

Detailed socio-demographic data, clinical history regarding duration of diabetes, presence of other comorbidities, medications consumed, previous hospitalization and /or major /minor surgical/interventional procedures were collected. Clinical examinations including blood pressure in sitting right arm position, and all other systemic examinations were conducted. Anthropometric dimensions - waist circumference (WC), and hip circumference (HC) were estimated, WC after normal exhalation in horizontal position just above the iliac crest, on empty stomach, with participant in erect and looking forward position. HC was measured in centimeters at 7 -8 inches from the waist by wrapping the tape at the maximum girth around hips. Waist-hip Ratio (WHR) was determined as ratio of WC to HC (in centimeters).

Serum fasting testosterone levels (nmol/L) were estimated in diabetes patients. Blood samples for estimating fasting serum testosterone, glucose levels and glycated hemoglobin (HbA1c) were taken while the patient had been admitted for angiogram. Patients who met the following criteria were included

- Random blood glucose value ≥ 11.1 (200 mg/dL) or
- Fasting plasma sugar ≥ 126 mg/dL) or
- Glycosylated Hemoglobin i.e. HbA1c $\geq 6.5\%$ or
- 2-h plasma sugar ≥ 200 mg/dL) - oral glucose tolerance test.

In females, no specific menstrual phase was considered for testosterone estimation. Testosterone values were estimated using Enzyme Linked Immuno-Sorbent Assay (ELISA) using 96 well kit. Based on the manufacturer instructions standard, control and test samples were admixed in the microtitre wells using enzyme conjugate. This mixture was processed through incubation, rinsing, absorption, further incubation to secure a color to the solution. This was then read, and concentration of testosterone was decided based on reference range of 2 to 9 ng/ml as provided by the manufacturer of the analyzer. Coronary angiogram was studied for number and extent of involvement of vessels.

Statistical analysis

Data collected was statistically analyzed using IBM SPSS version 22 for association between serum testosterone, WHR, glycemic index and extent of CAD, Serum testosterone level was considered as the primary variable; CAD, extent of CAD were outcome variables. Normal distribution was checked. Descriptive analyses are expressed as mean \pm standard deviation for quantitative variables; frequency, and proportion are mentioned for categorical variables. Average values were compared between study groups using Independent sample t-test (2 groups)/ ANOVA (>2 groups). p value < 0.05 was considered statistically significant.

Results:**Sample characteristics:**

165 subjects were analyzed, 109 males (66.1%) and 56 females (33.9%). Majority patients were >45 years of age. Descriptive data of participants has been tabulated in Table 1.

Table 1 Socio – Demographic Details of Participants

Characters	Sub groups	N(%)
Gender	Male	109(66.1)
	Female	56(33.9)
Age in years	18 to 45	18(10.9)
	>45	147(89.1)
Coronary Artery Disease	Present	128(77.6)
		Males 92(55.8)
	Females 36(21.8)	
	Absent	37(22.4)
Males 17(10.1)		
Females 20(12.3)		
Diabetes	HbA1c \geq 9	Males 13(7.8)
		Females 21(12.7)
	HbA1c <9	Males 96(58.2)
		Females 35(21.3)
Hypertension	Present	85(51.5)
	Absent	80 (48.5)
Total		165 (100)

Coronary angiogram was studied. Subjects were grouped as per the number of coronary arteries diseased into single, double, and triple vessel CAD, as seen in Table 2.

Table 2 Descriptive Analysis of Extent of CAD in Study Population (N=165)

CAD	Severity of CAD	Males	Females	N (%)
Present	Single Artery Disease SAD	39	20	59(35.8)
	Double Artery Disease (DAD)	28	8	36(21.8)
	Triple Artery Disease (TAD)	25	8	33(20)
				128(77.6)
Absent		17	20	37(22.4)
			Total	165 (100)

Left anterior descending (LAD-50.3%), right coronary artery (RCA- 37.6%) and left circumflex artery (LCX- 31.5%) were the commonly affected vessels. Ramus (1.8%) and diagonal (1.8%) branches were least affected. WHR and HbA1c values of patients were correlated with presence of CAD as seen in Table 3.

Table 3 Clinical Parameters of Participants (N=165)

Parameter	Mean ± SD	Minimum	Maximum
Waist Hip Ratio	0.91 ± 0.05	0.8	1.1
HbA1c %	8.05 ± 1.19	6.5	12.0
Serum testosterone levels ng/ml	3.95 ± 2.08	0.2	8.6

There was weak negative not statistically significant correlation linking WHR and serum testosterone values (r value= -0.124) for males. In females, WHR and serum testosterone levels (r value=0.066) showed weak positive correlation though not statistically significant. Out of 128 participants with presence of CAD 28 (21.88%) had a HbA1c level ≥ 9 while it was < 9 for 100 (78.13%) participants. Out of 37 participants with absence of CAD, the HbA1c level was ≥ 9 for 6 (16.22%) participants while it was < 9 for 31 (83.78%) participants. The difference in the proportion of presence or absence of CAD with varying HbA1c levels was statistically not significant (p value 0.454). For patients with HbA1c levels ≥ 9 , serum testosterone and CAD association in both genders was statistically not significant (p value > 0.05). Testosterone values in male patients with TAD CAD were lower compared to patients with single or double CAD and 'no' CAD, Table 4. However, in females with triple vessel CAD, testosterone values were higher than other female study subjects, Table 4.

Table 4 Comparison of Mean Serum Testosterone Values and Extent of CAD

Severity of CAD	Male Serum testosterone levels ng/ml (Mean ±SD)
No (n=17)	4.5 ± 1.82
Yes (n=92)	4.02 ± 1.72
Single Vessel Disease	4.09 ± 2.02
Double Vessel Disease	3.96 ± 1.48
Triple Vessel Disease	3.99 ± 1.53
	Female Serum testosterone levels ng/ml (Mean ±SD)
No (n=20)	1.3 ± 1.34
Yes (n=36)	1.3 ± 1.3
SAD	0.86 ± 0.73
DAD	1.6 ± 1.57
TAD	2.24 ± 1.9

Discussion:

Burden of diabetes in India will almost double from 40.9 million in 2007, to projected 80.9 million by 2025 [16]. Many risk factors contributing to CAD among diabetes population have been studied extensively. Recent study has showed testosterone may be used as marker of CAD and may even be used as its predictor [17]. Similar study has shown an increased prevalence of CAD in diabetes men as compared to women [18]. Studies of correlation between hormones

and CAD exist, but further considering genders and diabetes have not been extensively done especially in Indian context. We have tried to correlate between serum testosterone levels, waist-hip ratio (WHR) and extent of CAD in diabetes of both genders.

A total of 165 diabetes patients coming to hospital for CAD related issues were analyzed. Most of the participants were aged greater than 45 years (89.09%) with 10.91% of subjects less than 45 years (table1). Majority were males, 66.1% while women were 33.9%, similar to other studies showing higher incidence rates of coronary heart disease(CHD) in diabetes men as compared to women [18]. 77.6% of our study population had CAD, of them 35.8% had SAD, 21.3% DAD and 20% with TAD. Only 22.4% of the participants did not have CAD (table 3). A study by Parsa, A et al [19], which included 5 subjects with 22% of diabetes population showed 10.9% patients had SAD and 89.1% had multi-vessel involvement. Another study by Naghshtabrizi, B et al [20], with 1100 study population found TAD greater in diabetes and hypertensive population. However, in our study we had a greater proportion of patients with SAD (35.8%), than multi-vessel disease.

Serum testosterone values and waist hip ratio association

Anthropometric parameters like WC and WHR are used to determine obesity and overweight in general population. Both are related to insulin resistance and CAD. Studies have linked low testosterone levels with insulin resistance and obesity [21]. Svartberg, J et al [22], found significant association between waist circumference and testosterone values, with decreased testosterone in subjects with high waist circumference. Karakas et al [23] showed an inverse relation of testosterone levels to BMI and WHR but correlation was irrelevant in women. Our study shows WHR is negatively correlated to serum testosterone values (r value -0.124), table 3, though not statistically significant (p value 0.200) for males. Values amongst female subjects revealed weak positive correlation linking WHR and testosterone levels (r value 0.066) but not statistically significant (p value 0.629).

Offender vessels involved in patients with CAD

Nearly half of our study participants were found to have involvement of left anterior descending artery-LAD (50.3%), followed by right circumflex -RCA (37.6%), left circumflex -LCX (31.5%), obtuse marginal – OM (10.9%), posterior descending - PDA (3%), ramus in 3 (1.8%), left main for 8 (4.7%), and diagonal artery in 3 (1.8%) participants, 23% of participants were found to have normal coronaries. In a similar study, Bhat et al [24], noted the most common offender vessel was LAD in (78.26%), followed by RCA (13.04%) and LCX in (8.70%) in their < 45yrs study subjects.

Serum testosterone levels and CAD in men:

Among the participants, the difference between mean serum testosterone values in males for presence and absence of CAD was (p value 0.301), not statistically significant. Serum Testosterone values on average in a total of 109 male participants was 3.95 ng/ml. Serum testosterone levels were marginally higher in the no CAD (4.5 ± 1.82 ng/ml) group when compared with the other group (4.02 ± 1.72 ng/ml) but not statistically significant.

Serum testosterone levels and extent of CAD in males:

When serum testosterone levels were compared with the extent of CAD, (table 3) we found testosterone levels were marginally higher in the no CAD group when correlated to the other group but statistically not significant (p value >0.05). Alkamel, A et al [25], considered a low testosterone cut off value of 2.5 ng/ml to show both low free and total testosterone were significantly present in CAD patients with diabetes, along with an increase in the extent of vessel involvement. Our study findings corroborate with this study. We also noted that in our study the average serum testosterone values in diabetes devoid of CAD was found to be around 4.5 ± 1.82 ng/ml which is consistent with the testosterone levels found in other studies [26].

Relationship between serum testosterone, extent of CAD and HbA1c in males

For the purpose of our study we further segregated our diabetes patients into two groups as HbA1c >9 and HbA1c <9 . We found in males with HbA1c >9 , mean serum testosterone values were more in subjects with SAD and less in those with TAD. Whereas among participants with HbA1c levels <9 serum testosterone values were higher in participants with TAD compared to SAD and DAD patients. Our findings were not statistically significant (p value >0.05). Similar other studies showed testosterone hormone did not correlate with HbA1c values in diabetes patients [27,28].

Relationship between testosterone values and CAD in women

Mean values of serum testosterone in females having or devoid of CAD was almost same (table 2,3) however, not statistically significant (p value 0.988).

Serum testosterone levels and extent of CAD in females

When serum testosterone levels were compared with the extent of CAD, in contrast to males, female participants' testosterone values showed an inverse relation to CAD. Studies in women, have shown a heterogeneous association of testosterone levels with diabetes and CAD. Few studies mention increase in baseline testosterone levels is related to CVS risk factors, insulin

resistance, obesity and type 2 diabetes mellitus [29-31]. There was no link between testosterone levels and CAD among diabetes women, however, women in DAD and TAD groups showed more concentration of serum testosterone compared to women without CAD. The lack of substantial study data on testosterone values among women could be one of the reasons for such varied results on the association of testosterone with CAD in diabetes women.

Relationship between serum testosterone, extent of CAD and HbA1c in females

Among the study population for HbA1c levels >9 in females, mean serum testosterone levels when compared between patients with and without CAD there was no statistically significant variation (p value >0.05). In females whose HbA1c >9, patients with TAD had least HbA1c levels; similar to that observed in males with HbA1c levels >9. For females with HbA1c levels < 9, difference in mean values for serum testosterone levels between with and without CAD groups were statistically not significant (p value >0.05), however, patients with TAD had higher serum testosterone levels than those with DAD and SAD, this was in accordance with our finding among male participants with HbA1c levels < 9.

Comparison of Serum testosterone levels and affected vessels for males and females

Mean serum testosterone levels of patients and the various vessels involved were compared among males and females separately, to check for an association, it was found that in males with LAD involvement testosterone levels were 4.05 ± 1.58 ng/ml and in males without LAD involvement testosterone levels were 4.16 ± 1.95 ng/ml, but it was not statistically significant. Similarly, in females with LAD involvement, its association with serum testosterone levels was statistically not significant. The second and third most commonly involved vessels RCA and LCX were not significantly in association with mean serum testosterone values. However, in females with / without involvement of obtuse marginal (OM), average serum testosterone levels showed statistically significant difference with p value 0.001. When males with OM involvement were assessed, no such association was seen. The proportion of participants with presence and absence of CAD with HbA1c levels >9 and HbA1c levels <9 is almost similar. In a study done by Gerstein HC, et al it was revealed that the role of intensive glycemic control for lowering cardiovascular risk has not been proved clearly in people with T2DM [32]. In our study we observed no significant difference in presence or absence of angiographically proven CAD with varying glycemic control.

In line with our study Arnlöv, J et al [33] found no association of testosterone with CAD. These heterogeneous findings about testosterone and coronary artery disease association shows that

further studies with larger populations might be required to establish a definitive relationship between testosterone and CAD among both diabetes males and females.

Conclusion:

In diabetes men higher serum testosterone levels were associated with protection from CAD. In diabetes women, testosterone levels did not seem to have protective effect against CAD. Poor glycemic control and lower testosterone values showed higher extent of CAD. Both in men and women, good glycemic control and higher levels of serum testosterone did not confer any beneficial effect against CAD. WHR in males showed inverse correlation to presence of CAD. In females WHR did not show any significant association with CAD.

Limitations:

Our study was time-bound, conducted in tertiary care hospital in south Indian city with small sample size. Due to this, authors could not evaluate the association between serum testosterone levels and extent of CAD after adjustment for dyslipidemia, hypertension, smoking, body mass index, which are risk factors for CAD through multivariate analysis. We did not assess the patients for other sex hormone levels such as sex binding hormone globulin, luteinising hormone and follicle stimulating hormone. We did not assess female participants at a specific point of their menstrual cycle nor were other sex hormones analysed.

Disclosure statement:

None of the authors have any potential conflicts of interest associated with this research.

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Nil.

Author contributions:

AS and SJ have made substantial contributions to the conception and design of the manuscript, PK, RS and SJ were involved in the acquisition of data, SJ and AS were instrumental in analysis and interpretation of the data. PAS, RS and SJ played a pivotal role in drafting this manuscript. All authors reviewed and approved the final manuscript and agree to be held accountable for all aspects of the work.

Consent to participate:

Written and informed consent was taken from the participants before commencing the study.

Ethical Statement:

Study was initiated after the approval and clearance from institutional Ethics Committee (IEC KMC MLR 09-18/259), Kasturba Medical College, Mangalore.

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Data availability statement:

The data that support the findings of this study can be provided by the authors, [JS, PAS], upon reasonable request.

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